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MARKETING TOOLS FOR PROMOTING GASTRONOMIC BRANDS IN TOURISM

Abstract. *The development of a program for promoting specialized tourist products with gastronomic elements, at the stage of emerging demand requires the use of special marketing tools. The article reveals the marketing essence of the gastronomic tourist product and justifies the use of gastronomic branding as a fundamental tool for market positioning and promotion in a competitive market. An overview of the regional resource potential for discovering the recognizable regional gastronomic brands and gastronomic tourism practices substantiate the need to distinguish gastronomic tourism into an independent promising part of the industry. The results of the analysis of international experience in promoting gastronomic brands and products can be adapted to the conditions of the Russian Federation and used in building a national development concept of gastronomic tourism. The optimal form of marketing support for the gastronomic tourism development, taking into account the influence of current environmental factors, can be considered the creation of regional multifunctional digital platforms combining gastronomic tourism facilities into a single network, complete the tour program, promote finished products, and also enable the tourist to independently draw up a route based on individual preferences. It was shown that as accompanying marketing tools it is advisable to use: event calendars, regional exhibitions and fairs of gastronomic topics, independent positioning of gastronomic objects as centers of tourist attraction.*

Keywords: *gastronomic tourism, brand, tourist product, promotion, marketing, tools*

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МАРКЕТИНГОВЫЕ ИНСТРУМЕНТЫ ПРОДВИЖЕНИЯ ГАСТРОНОМИЧЕСКИХ БРЕНДОВ В СФЕРЕ ТУРИЗМА

Разработка программы продвижения специализированных туристских продуктов, к которым относится продукт гастрономического туризма, на стадии формирующегося спроса требует использования специальных маркетинговых инструментов. В статье раскрывается сущность гастрономического турпродукта с позиции значимых в разрезе маркетинга характеристик и обосновывается использование гастрономического брендинга как основополагающего инструмента рыночного позиционирования и продвижения в условиях конкурентного рынка. Обзор регионального ресурсного потенциала в части наличия узнаваемых региональных гастрономических брендов и организационно-экономического опыта в данном сегменте туристского обслуживания позволяют сделать вывод о целесообразности выделения этого продукта в самостоятельный перспективный для развития вид. Результаты проведённого анализа международного опыта продвижения гастрономических брендов и продуктов могут быть адаптированы к условиям России и использованы при построении национальной концепции развития гастрономического туризма. Оптимальной формой маркетинговой поддержки развития гастрономического туризма с учётом влияния текущих факторов внешней среды можно считать создание региональных multifunctional цифровых платформ, позволяющих объединить объекты гастрономического туризма в единую сеть, комплектовать программу тура, продвигать готовые продукты, а также давать возможность туристу самостоятельно составить маршрут, опираясь на индивидуальные предпочтения. Было показано, что в качестве сопутствующих маркетинговых инструментов целесообразно использовать: событийные календари, региональные выставки и ярмарки гастрономической тематики, самостоятельное позиционирование гастрономических объектов как центров туристского притяжения.

Ключевые слова: *гастрономический туризм, бренд, туристский продукт, продвижение, маркетинг, инструменты*

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Introduction

The market of tourist and recreational services of the Russian Federation is undergoing significant changes due to the impact of a combination of simultaneously affecting geopolitical and economic factors. Market experts, assessing the current state of the external environment and its instability, agree that the demand for tourism services in the coming years will be satisfied mainly due to the supply generated in the domestic market. In this regard, the development of new forms of regional tourism offers and its marketing promotion becomes relevant. The level of development of gastronomic tourism in Russia as an independent, separate type gives reason to attribute it to a relatively new type of tourism activity (according to the Interfax-tourism news agency, the average level of the share of gastronomic tours in the total tourist flow in the regions of the Russian Federation is 8-10%)¹. At the same time, it is impossible to regard gastronomy as a fundamentally new activity for travelers, since catering services are among the basic services of any tourist product. In this regard, the marketing positioning of this type of tourism is primarily aimed at forming a segment of consumers who choose to get acquainted with new gastronomic products, national culinary traditions of the peoples of Russia, thereby expanding their gastronomic experience and taste sensations.

Analysis of publications on this topic

The development of gastronomic tourism in the Russia at the present stage is in the process of formation and gradual strengthening of the product position in the system of tourist offer, expanding the number of the target audience by increasing its interest in the opportunity to eat tasty and varied, join a healthy lifestyle and nutrition, consume environmentally friendly and natural products while traveling, expand your culinary skills with the interactive component of the tour package.

The issues of the development of gastronomic tourism are partially reflected in the works of domestic and foreign authors, in

particular P. P. Chuvatkin, L. A. Moreva, M.S. Oborin, V.Sh. Khetagurova, Yu. Yu. Shvetc, A. I. Mosalev, M. V. Rosser, C. Wang, N. Zigern-Korn, who studied the foundations of the formation of gastronomic tourism and the peculiarities of its development. A significant part of the research on the relevance of developed gastronomic tourism, its immediate significance and importance, as an integral component of the cultural and historical heritage of peoples and ethnic groups, the impact of branding on territorial development is contained in the scientific journals *Service and Tourism: Current Challenges*, *Bulletin of the National Academy of Tourism*, *Bulletin of the Academy of Knowledge*. A large number of studies on this topic were presented at the conference *Tourism and National Projects of the Russian Federation*, in Sochi in October 2020. The basics of marketing tools for promoting tourist products are contained in the works of Voinova Ya. A. [5, 7, 9].

The study of the practice of using marketing tools for promoting gastronomic brands was carried out using the works of foreign and domestic authors in the field of tourism economics reflecting the peculiarities of the functioning of various tourist activities within the framework of the tourist destination.

Methods and methodology

The materials of the study were the works of domestic and foreign authors [1, 2] in the field of ethnic and gastronomic tourism (Chuvatkin P. P., Oborin M. S., Khetagurova V. Sh., Shabalina N. V., Fomin A. A.) [4, 5, 6], as well as in the field of marketing research (Durovich A. P., Voinova Ya. A., Frolova E. V., Arslanova G. Kh.) [3, 4, 8]. The basis of this study was the analysis of the experience of implementing marketing tools for the promotion of territorial brands, structural and functional analysis of domestic and foreign practices of marketing promotion, a systematic analysis of functional features and digital promotion of gastronomic tourism products on the market.

Discussion

Most regions of the Russian Federation

¹ Interfax Tourism News Agency. URL: <https://tourism.interfax.ru> (Accessed on September 22, 2022).

have a high culinary and gastronomic potential, the full inclusion of which in the tourist turnover will create a product whose supply volume will significantly exceed the level of current demand. Thus, this product at the current stage of the life cycle needs significant marketing support, the main task of which is to positively present such a travel program. Managers involved in the sale of gastronomic products must have knowledge of the technologies for manufacturing local products, the history of traditional dishes and drinks, the peculiarities of regional production of products, including those related to folk crafts, culture and traditions of the small peoples of Russia, and be able to use the totality of these ideas about the product in order to stimulate consumer interest in making such a trip.

The origins of tourist motivation are associated with the cultural and educational function of gastronomic tourism and boil down to the desire of the consumer through the physiological sensitive functions of the body and taste buds to study the cultural and historical features of cooking that give food products specific properties, take part in the feasting events of local communities and learn non-traditional ways of eating. food, thereby joining the world cultural heritage, centuries-old traditions, customs of life and management of local peoples, to feel the traditional ethnic life and the specifics of the cuisines of the peoples of the world.

Thus, gastronomic tourism can be regarded as a conductor in the popularization of national cultural values, promotion of intercultural exchange and ensuring the connection of peoples and civilizations [1].

Gastronomic tourism is based on a symbiosis of cultural, educational, historical, patriotic, ethnic, event, ecological, rural tourism, combining certain elements of each of them in a gastronomic tourist product.

The assessment of the feasibility of creating a gastronomic tourism product and the forecast of its market potential are based on the analysis of objects that have a set of properties that give reason to include them in the gastronomic tour program. Such objects may

include:

- regions associated with the production of certain products of territorial affiliation;
- farms and estates of a full reproduction cycle, providing a full range of services as part of the tourist product;
- objects of excursion and interactive gastronomic display, including manufacturing enterprises known for their culinary products, enterprises organizing master classes and interactive programs for visitors;
- conceptual cafes and restaurants representing national or regional specifics of cooking in an open kitchen;
- event culinary events (gastronomic festivals, holidays, fairs, tastings);
- cultural and educational institutions (museums, gastronomy schools, culinary workshops).

Marketers involved in the creation and promotion of gastronomic tours need to take into account the specifics of gastronomic tourism, which is a set of activities implemented within a certain territory, including acquaintance with the traditions of local cuisine, gastronomic territorial brands, technologies for preparing traditional dishes and features of production, management and life, as well as cultural, educational and recreational activities and subsequent tasting, allowing you to form a multidimensional idea of the region [2]. The implementation of gastronomic programs should contribute to the preservation of the world cultural and historical heritage and ensure the connection of countries, peoples and civilizations through the popularization and promotion of gastronomic traditions and customs of the peoples of the world.

The source of compensation for the costs of active regional marketing of gastronomic tourism will be an increase in cash flows to the region by stimulating the economic activity of the main and related industries included in the process of serving travelers. In addition, gastronomic tourism acts as a multiplier that contributes to the emergence of additional jobs, the development of tourist and service infrastructure, ensuring the

tourist attractiveness of the territory, as well as the formation of strong intercultural ties.

Marketing decisions on the develop-

ment of a gastronomic product can be based on a wide range of its socio-economic functions, presented in fig. 1.

Fig. 1 – Functions of gastronomic tourism

Currently, gastronomic tourism in the Russian Federation is developing at a stable pace, provided by a shift in tourist flows in the direction of diversifying the national tourist offer and an educational interest in new tourist routes and products. According to the Federal Agency for Tourism, the growth of the domestic gastronomic tourism market in the Russian Federation after a sharp decline in 2019–2020. amounted to about 400% at the beginning of 2022, which indicates a high demand for gastronomic tours among consumers².

Market conditions indicate that in the current conditions, the most common product of gastronomic tourism are sightseeing tours and short gastronomic trips to attend event events, master classes, training programs. At the same time, there is a weak degree of state

support for entrepreneurial initiatives, low interest of business, a tense socio-economic situation in society, which together causes difficulties in the development of gastronomic tourism in the regions [3].

Marketing efforts of regional authorities and commercial structures represented by tour operators should be reduced to the formation of recognizable gastronomic brands that can fully reflect the uniqueness of the tourist offer and ensure the growth of the tourist flow, increase profits, increase the investment attractiveness of the destination, becoming, in fact, the most important marketing tool positioning and promotion of a local product. In the context of a tense geopolitical situation, the formation of territorial brands, including gastronomic ones, is one of the priorities in the context of achieving the goal of

² Official website of the Federal Agency for Tourism of the Russian Federation. URL: <https://russiatourism.ru> (Assessed on August 24, 2022)

developing domestic tourism in the Russian Federation [4]. The high level of saturation of the tourist market with a variety of products determines the relevance of developing methods and technologies for promoting tourist areas through gastronomic brands in order to increase their competitiveness in this segment [5].

The use of marketing methods and tools for promoting gastronomic brands will solve the following tasks:

- ✓ reduce the uncertainty of the tourist when choosing a tourist destination;
- ✓ to form a clear idea of the visited territory, the advantages and specifics of the tourist destination;
- ✓ increase the level of customer loyalty;
- ✓ visualize the brand in order to obtain competitive advantages;
- ✓ create a gastronomic image of the territory.

The presence of recognizable gastronomic brands associated with regions determines their gastronomic attractiveness, based on the basic human need for food, as well as consumer cultural and educational interest. Culinary features and traditions of management, according to consumer preferences, determine the orientation of tourist routes (30% of tourists choose a tourist product based on the gastronomic characteristics of the region) [6].

The specificity of gastronomic traditions, the peculiarities of regional crafts and production technologies, authentic national dishes and culinary traditions of the people's characteristic of each region of Russia, determine the emergence of a trend to include gastronomic facilities in tourist service programs and highlight gastronomic specifics as the basic tourist brand of the territory [7].

The growing importance of the culture of food consumption, the development of the restaurant business, the popularization of gastronomic content, have formed the gastronomic image of the regions thanks to iconic gastronomic elements (brand, events, places).

Each region has its own specific gastronomic brands that have made the destination popular: chak-chak, bishbarmak in the

Republic of Tatarstan, bonito stroganina in the Kaliningrad region, khinkali-like buuzas in Buryatia, gingerbread in the Tula region, small meat pies posikunchiki in the Perm region, Vologda butter, Ossetian pies, Adyghe cheese; Astrakhan watermelons, etc.

The world experience in promoting gastronomic brands is associated with the formation of event events and a system of associative consumption of products and may be of interest in the formation of a national concept for the development of gastronomic tourism (Table 1).

Research results

Thus, the presence of the gastronomic potential of the territory allows us to propose a mechanism for promoting gastronomic brands to ensure the tourist attractiveness of the region and the formation of a competitive gastronomic tourism product in order to develop gastronomic tourism in the regions of the Russian Federation.

As a substantive part of the promotion mechanism, one can define tools aimed at solving the problems of increasing the recognition of gastronomic brands, expanding the target audience, increasing market share, and attracting additional tourist flow.

As part of solving the problems of promoting gastronomic brands, it is possible to use a set of marketing tools aimed at creating a unique image of the territory for the tourist and enhancing its tourist attractiveness [8].

1. Creation of a digital tourism platform for the development of gastronomic tourism, which is designed to provide coordinating support for the choice of gastronomic tourism products, drawing up a tour route, choosing accommodation facilities, meals, an interactive part of the product, depending on the individual preferences of tourists (Fig. 2).

The possibility of this digital platform will be a targeted approach to determining the basic content of the tourism product. Depending on the choice of objects of gastronomic tourism, an alternative choice of the main and additional tour packages is determined.

The platform approach will minimize the cost of the consumer to search, select,

package and purchase a gastronomic tourist product, providing information accessibility about prices, quality and quantity of goods

and services provided, as well as about the content of the product, depending on the purpose of travel [9].

Table 1 – Global gastronomic brands

<i>Country</i>	<i>Gastronomic specialization</i>	<i>Gastronomic events</i>	<i>Gastronomic brands</i>
Italy	National Italian cuisine, wine tours, cheese tours, ethnic tours, rural tours, cooking classes, restaurant tours	Pizza Fest in Naples, l'Primi D'Italia in Foligno	Tuscan wine, Chianti, Nobile, Montepulciano, Ornellaia, Masseto, Sassicaia, Truffles from Piedmont, Gorgonzola, Mozzarella
Germany	National German cuisine of various regional localization, beer tours, wine tours, cheese tours, festivals	Beer Festival – Oktoberfest	Bavarian sausages, Christstollen, Pork knuckle, Riesling
France	National French cuisine, wine tourism, cheese tourism	Wine Festival – Chardonnay	Ratatouille, Provence wine, Champagne, Chianti
Spain	National Spanish cuisine	Gastro Festival in Madrid, Food Festival in Barcelona, Feast of olives	Tapas, Paella, Jamón
Georgian	National Georgian cuisine wine tours, cheese tours	Cheese Festival, Wine Festival	Khachapuri, Chahohbili, Borjomi Mineral Water
Turkey	National Turkish cuisine, oriental sweets	GastroFest Turkey, International Street Food Festival	Semite, Baklava, Kebab, Lukum
Morocco	National Moroccan cuisine, tea ceremony	Moroccan Food Festival	Tajin, Couscous
USA	Gastronomic tours, fast food festivals FastFood	Beer Festival, Food and Wine Festival	Donats, Muffin, Brownie
Canada	Agrotourism, restaurant tours, local brands	The CARIBANA festival	Maple syrup
Mexico	National Mexican Cuisine Festivals	Aroma and Flavors, The Thousand Flavors of the Mole Route, The Kings Festival	Burrito, Tortilla, Salsa
Peru	National Peruvian cuisine, chocolate tours	Mistura Food Festival	Chocolat
India	Indian National Cuisine, Tea Tours, Spice and Spice Tours	Goa Food and Culture Festival, Delhi Spring Food Festival, Food Fest 2016	Spices
Japan	National cuisine	Ramen Expo Culinary Exhibition, Kyushu Beer Festival, Mochitsuki Sweet Festival	Fish – Fugu, Sushi, Wasabi, To Saca, Motya
China	National cuisine (traditional Chinese boxed food)	Asian Gastronomic Festival	Peking Duck

2. Creation of a gastronomic event calendar that ensures the creation and strengthening of gastronomic brands that identify the territory and form an associative perception of the region (Astrakhan watermelons, Krasnopolyansk tea, Black Sea flounder, Sakhalin caviar, etc.). Thus, it is gastronomic brands

that will act as a motive for visiting the destination.

3. Restaurant branding, which attracts additional tourist flow to the region. Restaurants and catering establishments, implementing unique concepts, create a favorable image that motivates tourists to travel, and

Fig. 2 – Digital platform for gastronomic tourism

act as "points of attraction" (White rabbit family restaurants are popular and attract tourists, Starbucks coffee chain is currently an object of tourist attraction, etc.).

4. Product branding that implements regional cuisine. Public catering enterprises, factories, farms, selling individual products, form gastronomic local brands for food systems (the Sochi local cuisine brand combines Caucasian culinary traditions in a modern interpretation - "khinkali with crab", "crab and shrimp kebab", "octopus with spicy Caucasian sauce"; the brand of Far Eastern cuisine implements conceptual dishes using regional seafood in the author's vision - Sakhalin crab determines the motivational culinary preferences of tourists in the Far East region; wine production enterprises of the Kuban form a gastronomic interest in excursions to the production base of farms and participation in tasting ceremonies).

5. The Museum of Regional Products provides advertising for unique food gastronomic

brands (Museum of Kolomna Pastila, Museum of Zarsk Gingerbread, Museum of Chocolate), popularizing the product and the territory.

6. Souvenir products, which have unique taste and external properties, provide direct advertising for gastronomic product brands due to their transportability, including among geographically remote consumers (Tula gingerbread appeals to consumer interest and associative demand for tourist products in the Tula region).

Conclusion

For the successful use of marketing tools for the promotion of gastronomic brands and their associated territories, it is necessary to determine the methods of advertising promotion: advertising in the media, media advertising, outdoor advertising, organizing various thematic events, presentation handouts, Internet marketing aimed at providing information and supporting gastronomic tourism. offers and promotion of gastronomic brands.

References

1. Aleksandrova, A. Yu. (2018). Turizm i kul'turnoye naslediye [Tourism and cultural heritage]. In: *Mezhvuzovskiy sbornik nauchnykh trudov [Intercollegiate collection of scientific works]*, 10-18. (In Russ.).
2. Andreeva, A. Yu. (2019). *Novyye tekhnologii ustoychivogo razvitiya turisticheskoy industrii [New technologies for intensive development of the tourism industry]*. Moscow: YURGU. (In Russ.).
3. Arslanova, G. Kh., & Khismatullin, M. M. (2017). Problemy razvitiya predprinimatel'skoy deyatelnosti v industrii turizma i gostepriimstva [Problems of business development in the tourism and hospitality industry]. *Ekonomika i predprinimatel'stvo [Economics and entrepreneurship]*, 5, 942-945. (In Russ.).
4. Frolova, E. V. (2017). Faktory razvitiya turisticheskoy privlekatel'nosti munitsipal'nykh obrazovaniy Rossii [Factors of development of tourist attractiveness of municipalities of Russia]. *Voprosy gosudarstvennogo i munitsipal'nogo upravleniya [Issues of state and municipal administration]*, 3, 112-128. (In Russ.).
5. Oborin, M. S. (2021). Tendentsii formirovaniya gastronomicheskogo turizma kak sanostoyatel'nogo vida yslug [Gastronomic tourism as an independent type of services: Formation trends]. *Sovremennye problemy servisa i turizma [Service and Tourism: Current Challenges]*, 4, 17-28. (In Russ.).
6. Gataullina, S. Yu., & Topchiy, A. V. (2018). O sostoyanii metodicheskoy otsenki effektivnosti ekonomicheskoy turistskoy deyatelnosti v sfere zdravookhraneniya [On the state of methodological support for assessing the economic effectiveness of tourism activities in the region]. *Internet-zhurnal «Naukovedeniye» [Online journal "Science Science"]*, 23, 98-112. (In Russ.).
7. Margieva, N. T. (2020). Sfera turizma v Rossii: sostoyaniye i perspektivy razvitiya [Tourism in Russia: state and development prospects]. *Ekonomika i predprinimatel'stvo [Economy and entrepreneurship]*, 10-1, 141-145. (In Russ.).
8. Voiniva, Ya. A. (2019). Internet-marketing v prodvizhenii SPA-cururtf [Digital marketing in the SPA-resort product promoting]. In: *Aktualnie problemizelionoi arkhitekturi, grazhdanskogo i ekologicheskogo proektirovaniya [Topical Problems of Green Architecture, Civil and Environmental Engineering]*. Moscow: EDP Sciences. (In Russ.).
9. Zigern-Korn, N. (2020). Theoretical substantiation of the state policy for spatial development of tourism. *Bulletin of the Moscow State Regional University. Series: Natural Science*, 2, 30-39.